

Prevalence Of Thyroid Dysfunction In Clinically Diagnosed Down Syndrome Subjects

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 21,2023</p> <p>Accepted: February 22,2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Down Syndrome, Thyroid Dysfunction, Euthyroidism, Hypothyroidism, Hyperthyroidism, Sick Thyroid Syndrome</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10694267</p>	<p><i>Objective-To Determine the Prevalence of Thyroid dysfunction in clinically Diagnosed Down syndrome (DS) Subjects</i></p> <p><i>Methods- Cross sectional study was carried out at University of Lahore, Biochemistry Department to find out the Prevalence of Thyroid dysfunction in 50 clinically diagnosed Down syndrome subjects aged 4 months to 8 years of children visiting Pediatrics clinics of children hospital Lahore Pakistan from September 2018 to May 2019 by measuring thyroid function test (T3, T4, TSH),antithyroid antibodies(ATA) and karyotyping. The procedure was well tolerated by most of DS subjects and minimal inconvenience to their parents.</i></p> <p><i>Results- To obtain better results, total 50 DS children were included in the study and found majority of the children were Males 33(66.0%) while 17(34.0%) were Female. Thyroid dysfunction was found in 27(54%) of DS subjects, of whom 13(26.0%) had Hypothyroidism, 08(16.0%) were having Subclinical hypothyroidism, 01(2.0%) had Sick thyroid syndrome, 4(8.0%) were Hyperthyroidism and 01(2.0%) were Subclinical hyperthyroidism. ATA was positive in 07(14.0%) patients of DS, of whom 02(28%) were Male and 05 were Female (72%), 03 had Hypothyroidim, 02 had Hyperthyroidism, 02 had Subclinical hypothyroidism. Remaining 23(46.0%) were having Euthyroidism.</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion-Researcher found a high Prevalence of Thyroid dysfunction in clinically diagnosed Down syndrome subjects.</i></p>

Introduction

Down syndrome is the fourth most common genetic disorder worldwide, Characterized by a full or partial extra copy of chromosome 21^{1,2}. Prevalence of Down syndrome is 1 out of 700-1000, live births which is 0.1%.³

There are three types of Down syndrome including 95% Nondisjunction, 2-4% Mosaicism and 2-6% Translocation. The Frequency of DS increases with increasing maternal age, oxidative stress, Alcohol, smoking at time of pregnancy, consanguineous marriages, certain diets, air pollutions, decrease levels of (selenium, vitamin E ,vitamin C, vitamin A, uric acid, Glutathione) Even very young mothers, maternal irradiation, fertility drugs, oral contraceptives, low folate levels, elevated plasma homocysteine levels and spermicides, phenylalanine hydroxylase activity impairment and over activity of DYRK1A Kinase may have a chance of a child with DS⁴. There are 6 million worldwide and 40000 people in USA are living with Down syndrome. According CDC, nearly 5500- 6,000 babies are born in USA with Down syndrome per year.^{5,6,7}

Down syndrome is associated with Thyroid disorders 10-94%.⁸ Subjects with Down syndrome (DS) are at increased risk for the development of all forms of thyroid disease: Hypothyroidism, Subclinical hypothyroidism (Hyperthyrotropenemia) ,Sick thyroid syndrome, Hyperthyroidism and Subclinical hyperthyroidism.³

Thyroid dysfunction in Down syndrome ranges from subclinical hypothyroidism (60-63%) to hypothyroidism (19.2%), sick thyroid syndrome, Autoimmune thyroiditis (6.5-34%), and hyperthyroidism 4.1% The Autoimmune thyroid disease(Hashimoto's thyroiditis=13-34% and Graves' disease(GD)=1.3-6.5%) with down syndrome have a higher prevalence than in general population.⁹

Frequency of thyroid diseases in patient with Down syndrome, starting in new born population is 0.7-1%, in children is 3-54% and in adults is 12-30%. The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) advises a screening protocol for thyroid function tests T3, T4, TSH and Anti thyroid antibodies in children with DS. This should be done at birth, at 6 months, 1 year, and annually up to age of 21 in order to avoid severe sequelae like irreversible Brain damages.^{5,10} Amniocentesis is done from 15 to 20 weeks of gestation, while Chorionic villus sampling from 9 to 14 weeks. In a karyotyping chromosomal analysis is done to confirm the diagnosis.⁶ Signs and symptoms of hypothyroidism can be difficult to discriminate from those found in the natural course of DS itself.⁵

There has yet no such study regarding association and prevalence of thyroid disorder in subjects with Down syndrome been found in Pakistan

Study was conducted by Dayal et al on 82 Down syndrome children and observed that, 76 patients had subclinical hypothyroidism (92.6%) while 6 (7.4%) had Hypothyroidism while among them 6 (7.4%) had positive antithyroid antibodies.¹¹

Study was undertaken by Cebeci et al on 62 DS children, 32 (51%) were male and 30 (49%) were female, it was observed that Hypothyroidism (27.1%) in which 1.8% hypothyroidism and 25.3% subclinical hypothyroidism, 8 of these had positive Antithyroid antibodies.¹² Research was performed by Purdy et al., 2014 on 122 children with Down syndrome with 32.5% had hypothyroidism, among them Hypothyroidism (17.5%), Subclinical hypothyroidism (15%) and sick thyroid syndrome 2.5%. (5) were observed. Survey was performed by Capone et al., 2018 on patients with Down syndrome and observed 27% had Hypothyroidism and subclinical hypothyroidism, 3% had Hyperthyroidism.¹³

Study was conducted by Nitash Zwaveling-Soonawala et al., 2017 on 90 children with DS. It was seen that 10 (17.2%) had hypothyroidism, in which 32% had positive antithyroid antibodies, 1.7% had hyperthyroidism.¹⁴ Study was conducted by de Asua et al., 2015 on Clinical on 144 adults with DS. It was observed that 51% were male, 49% were female, 56% had thyroid dysfunctions.¹⁵ Research was conducted by Sinai et al., 2018 on 251 individuals with DS and observed that 38.2% had thyroid dysfunction.⁷ Study was done by Aversa et al on DS children which showed, Hashimoto's thyroiditis (13-34%) and Graves' disease (6.5%). In Hashimoto's thyroiditis; Subclinical hypothyroidism 63.0%, Hypothyroidism 19.2% and Hyperthyroidism were 4.1%⁹

Survey was conducted by Pierce et al on 565 pediatric patients with DS. It was observed, male were (54%), 24% had thyroid dysfunction in which 7.3% had hypothyroidism, 10% subclinical hypothyroidism and 1.6% had hyperthyroidism (Graves' disease).³

Study was done by Anusandana Mahapatra et al on 65 patients with DS. It was found 19.4% had hypothyroidism.¹⁶ Research was done by Lavigne et al on 663 patients with DS. 19.0% (60/316) had hypothyroidism.¹⁷

Study was performed by Guaraldi et al on 105 DS patients. 41 (39%) had hypothyroidism. In another survey of 106 persons with DS, 5% had hypothyroidism, and 4% had subclinical hypothyroidisms. A subsequent study by Karlsson et al on 85 individuals found 35% (30/85) had hypothyroidism and 2.4% (2/85) had hyperthyroidism.¹⁸

Study was held by ER Villani et al on 105 patients with DS subjects, 39 (37%) were female and 61 (43%) were male patients, 39% had Hypothyroidism.¹⁹ Yousef abdulrazzaq et al 2018 conducted a study on 89 children of Down syndrome subjects. 18 (19.6%) had Hypothyroidism, of whom 3 (3.4%) had positive ATA, 87 (97.8%) had Non-disjunction of trisomy 21, 1 (1.1%) had Translocation and 1 (1.1%) had Mosaic.⁴ Pierce et al conducted a research on 159 patients with DS and observed that 24% had Subclinical hypothyroidism, 13% had Hypothyroidism.²⁰

Methodology

Cross sectional survey Purposive sampling technique was used. Sample size was calculated 50 through online calculator²¹ on basis of Prevalence 24% of Thyroid Dysfunction³ in Patients with Down syndrome by using 10% confidence interval and 90% confidence level. Study was conducted in university of Lahore at Biochemistry department. Patient with Down syndrome male and female were included and Current use of thyroxin or anti-thyroid hormone were excluded. Questioner was used for data collection develop from literature review and expert opinion. For data collection Consent was obtained from parents of all participants of study and permission was taken from institute. Karyotyping was conducted for confirmation of Down syndrome using Giemsa (G-Banding Technique) through cytogenetic analysis at Metaphase stage. The procedure was carried out within Glass safety cabinet to maintain sterility of specimen and protect operator from biological hazard. 3-5 ml Blood was drawn from selected patients into Na heparinized vacutainer tubes. Stock reagents (RPMI-1640 medium, fetal calf serum-Glutamine 200 Mm, penicillin streptomycin solution, phytohaemagglutinin) were dispensed in Labeled (Lab-No, Name of patient, Dated) T-25 cultural cell 50 ml Flask. Then heparinized bloods were mixed into that flask and incubated at 37°C for 72 hours. After that stock reagent 0.05 ml Colcemid solution was added and mixed in flask and incubated for 35 minutes. Then contents of flask were put into a screwed conical centrifuge tubes through pipette for centrifugation at 2000rpm for 5-7 minutes. Then supernatant was discarded. Pellet was resuspended. Then 0.075 ml KCl added and mixed into cell pellet and incubated at 37°C for 20 minutes. Tubes were again centrifuged at 2000rpm for 5-7 minutes. Again supernatant was discarded and pellet was resuspended. Fixative (3:1 Methanol, Glacial acetic acid) was added and mixed into cell pellet. Tubes were placed into incubator for 10 minutes at 10°C, which was centrifuged at 2000rpm for 5-7 minutes. Again supernatant was discarded and pellet was resuspended. This Fixative step was repeated until cell pellet at bottom was clear and white color. At end fixed cell suspension was kept in freezer at 20°C for slide making. Fixed cell suspension removed from freezer and centrifuged at 2000rpm for 5-7 min. Again supernatant

was discarded and pellet was resuspended with fresh fixative. There was milky appearance. 1-2 drops of fixative cell suspension were placed side by side on labeled slides by pipette. Then placed slides into hot air oven at 90 °C for one hour. Rinsed slides with Normal saline in 1st Coplin jar, then immersed slide into 2nd Coplin jar containing 70ml Trypsin for 10-60 seconds. Slides were then rinsed with Gurr buffer solution in 3rd Coplin jar. Slides were covered with Giemsa Stain solution in 4th Coplin jar for 3-6 minutes. Slides were then rinsed with tap water and placed in air to dry. Stained slides were examined under bright field microscope to assist Banding. 15-20 Metaphases were counted, out of these 10 were analysed for Banding pattern according to ISCN. Images of selected metaphases were captured through automated Karyotyping system and displayed on monitor screen to see karyotypes, Gender and chromosomal defects both numerical and structural. Metaphases were counted for chromosomal number, identification and defects.²²

After confirmation of Down syndrome by karyotyping genetic analysis, the individuals were tested for thyroid dysfunction. 5-10 ml venous Blood was drawn and collected in a vacutainer from patients with Down syndrome by using standard protocols. Thyroid function test including serum or plasma T3 and T4 determinations were made by chemiluminescent competitive immunoassay technique (samples [antibodies] were loaded with cuvettes/micro wells plates/micro sample cups in automated integrated system of Vitros machine which having already loaded refrigerated storage reagents (substrates), washing buffers, Diluents, waste box and computed programming etc: sample T3 and T4 (antibodies) with a reagent horseradish peroxidase HRP labeled T3 and T4 conjugate (antigen) coated on wells formed antigen antibody complex. Unbound materials were removed by washing. That complex was captured by an reagent sheep anti T3 and T4. Thyroxine binding globulin TBG were eliminated by buffer and blocking agents (stop) incubated for 29 minutes at 37°C. Unbound materials were removed by washing. Sheep anti T3 and T4 (substrate) were measured by luminescent reaction chemiluminescence immunoassay (automated analyzers) using an reagents luminol, peracid salts, electron transfer agent acetanilide in order to produce Light reaction. Light signals (photons) were read by the system. The amount of HRP labeled T3 and T4 conjugate was indirectly proportional to concentration of T3 and T4 present).

The serum or plasma TSH determinations were made by an chemiluminescent immunometric techniques (sample TSH with an reagent horseradish peroxidase HRP labeled TSH conjugate and biotinylated antibody formed antigen antibody complex which was captured by an reagent streptavidin incubated for 9 minutes at 37°C which was measured by luminescent reaction chemiluminescence immunoassay (automated analyzers) by using reagents luminol, peracid salts, electron transfer agent acetanilide in order to produce Light reaction. unbound reagents and samples were washed away by buffer. Light signals were read by the system microwell plates reader as a relative luminescent (light) intensity units (RLU). The amount of HRP labeled TSH conjugate was directly proportional to concentration of TSH present by using VITROS (ECI/ECIQ/3600 immunodiagnostic systems and the VITROS 5600XT/7600 Integrated systems.²³ while Antithyroid antibodies were done by using DIASTAT Test.²⁴ SPSS 22 was used for data analysis

Results

Table # 1 asserts T3, T4, TSH, ATA, and Karyotyping among 50 children with Down syndrome, Male and Female

Variables	Sub-variables	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	P-value
T3 ng/ml	Normal 0.80-1.79	24(48)	8(16)	0.098
	Below 0.80	8(16)	6(12)	
	Above 1.79	1(2)	3(6)	
T4 µg/dl	Normal 6.00-12.19	24(48)	8(16)	0.098
	Below 6.00	8(16)	6(12)	
	Above 12.19	1(2)	3(6)	
TSH µIU/ml	Normal 0.34-5.59	2(4)	3(6)	0.011
	Below 0.34	2(4)	4(8)	
	Above 5.59	11(22)	10(20)	
ATA	NA	20(40)	3(6)	0.07
	Positive	2(4)	5(10)	
	Negative	11(22)	9(18)	
Karyotyping	Non-disjunction	30(60)	16(32)	0.580
	Translocation	3(6)	1(2)	

Note: Antithyroid antibodies (ATA) Positive = Tg-ab \geq 4.11 IU/ML or TPO-ab $>$ 5.61 IU/ML, Negative = Tg-ab $<$ 4.11 IU/ML or TPO-ab = 5.61 IU/ML. NA = Not applicable. T3 = TRIIODOTHYRONINE. T4 = THYROXINE. TSH = THYROID STIMULATING HORMONE

P-value of TSH was found 0.011 among Male and Female, which is significant statistically

Table #2 shows Thyroid Function in children with Down syndrome

Variables	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	P value
Euthyroidism	20(40)	3(6)	0.039
Hypothyroidism	7(14)	6(12)	
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	4(8)	4(8)	
Sick thyroid syndrome	1(2)	0(0)	
Hyperthyroidism	1(2)	3(6)	
Subclinical Hyperthyroidism	0(0)	1(2)	

Table above shows that among 50 children of Down syndrome, Thyroid dysfunction was 27(54%) along with Male and Female p-value was 0.039, which is significant statistically

Discussion

Total 50 children of DS were included in the study and found majority of the children were Males 33(66.0%) while remaining proportion 17(34.0%) were Female. Vallani et al., 2016 showed Male were (59%) and Female were (38%) which is compatible to our study.¹⁹

Our study showed that among 50 children of Down syndrome, 46(92.0%) were having Non-disjunctional and 4(8%) Translocation types of DS. Study was presented by Asim et al., 2015 who reflected that 96-98% had Non-disjunctional and 2-4% Translocation types of DS which is comparable to our work.²⁰

Our study showed among 50 children of Down syndrome, 07(14.0%) were having positive antithyroid antibodies. Aversa et al., 2015 revealed in study that 6-34% had positive Antithyroid antibodies (ATA) which is compatible to our thesis work.⁹

Our study reflected that among 50 children of Down syndrome, 13(26.0%) were Hypothyroidism. The results of our study are comparable with the study done by Capone et al., 2018 who confirmed that 27% had hypothyroidism.¹³

Our study showed that among 50 children of Down syndrome, 08(16.0%) were Subclinical hypothyroidism. Similar results were presented by Purdy et al., 2014 confirmed that 15% had Subclinical hypothyroidism.⁵ Our study elucidated that among 50 children of Down syndrome, 01(2.0%) were Sick thyroid syndrome. Similar results were described by Purdy et al., 2014 depicted that 2.5% had Sick thyroid syndrome.⁵

Our study showed that among 50 children of Down syndrome, 4(8.0%) were Hyperthyroidism. Aversa et al., 2015 in study reflected that 4.1% had Hyperthyroidism which is comparable to our study.⁹

Our study reflected that among 50 children of Down syndrome, 01(2.0%) were having Subclinical hyperthyroidism. Tüysüz & Beker, 2001 demonstrated in study that 2(0.62%) had Subclinical hyperthyroidism which is comparable to our study.²⁵ Our study showed that among 50 children of Down syndrome, 27(54%) had Thyroid dysfunction in DS subjects. Ayub et al., 2017 asserted in study that 3-54% had Thyroid dysfunction which is compatible to our research work.¹⁰

Conclusions And Recommendations

Thyroid dysfunctions were found frequent endocrine disorders associated with Down syndrome subjects including Hypothyroidism, Subclinical hypothyroidism, Sick thyroid syndrome, Hyperthyroidism, Subclinical hyperthyroidism respectively.

There should be Regular thyroid function screening and follow up in all age groups of Down syndrome subjects.

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